

QoS and Burst Transmission Enabled MAC Protocol for Ambient IoT

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Abstract—Energy harvesting technology enables Internet of Things (IoT) devices to harvest energy from ambient sources like the sun, radio signals, and others. However, due to the uncertainty in available energy caused by surrounding conditions, these devices may face energy scarcity issues. This can be addressed by devising energy harvesting-aware schemes, such as Medium Access Control (MAC) protocols and task scheduling algorithms, to meet the desired application performance. For instance, a monitoring application generates periodic (low priority) and event-based (high priority) data traffic with different transmission requirements. Thus, such application requires minimum delay for high-priority packets under dynamic harvesting conditions. Nevertheless, the existing protocols for ambient-powered IoT have limited consideration in supporting low-priority packets, which often remain in the queue. As a result, these packets suffer longer delays and may even be dropped. This work proposes a Quality of Service (QoS) and burst transmission enabled protocol called QBT-MAC. QBT-MAC utilizes separate queues for both high and low priority data packets and introduces a burst transmission technique to minimize the delay and maximize the packet delivery ratio for low-priority packets. Simulation results show that QBT-MAC achieves better performance in terms of average delay, packet delivery ratio, and energy efficiency with improvements of up to 69.3%, 15.8%, and 13.6%, respectively when compared with QPPD-MAC and EEM-MAC protocols.

Keywords—Energy harvesting, MAC protocol, QoS-Aware, burst transmission, Internet of things, Ambient IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent years have witnessed a significant growth in Internet of Things (IoT) applications, such as smart cities, agriculture, environmental monitoring and others. The number of IoT devices are growing and it is expected to surpass 29 billion globally by 2030 [1]. Moreover, powering these IoT devices through batteries leads to limited network lifetime, higher deployment costs and negative impact on the environment [2]. Therefore, the growing number of IoT devices has increased the need of sustainable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly solutions.

Energy harvesting technology allows IoT devices to harvest energy from sustainable sources, such as solar, radio frequency (RF), wind, vibration and thermal [3]. Nevertheless, the dynamic harvesting rate due to the surrounding conditions such as rain, pressure has raised the challenge to meet the desired performance. For example, during rainy day, a solar powered device could become non-operational for a longer period of time. In monitoring

applications, IoT devices sense both periodic data i.e., temperature and humidity, and also event-based data such fire alert. Thus, the application requires event-based data to be delivered immediately with minimum delay. This drives the need to develop QoS and energy-harvesting aware schemes such as adaptive communication, and task scheduling algorithms to meet the desired performance level while ensuring sustainable network operation under different harvesting scenarios [3].

Several research works have been done to support QoS in ambient IoT. However, most of the existing communication protocols [4-16] have limited consideration in supporting both types of priority data packets under dynamic network conditions. Hence, ensuring minimum delay for the highest priority packets, while reducing delay and preventing loss of lower priority packets is also necessary for overall application performance. Therefore, this work presents a QoS aware MAC protocol that uses packet queuing and burst data transmission technique to support different priority packet and enhance the application's performance.

The contribution of the work is as follows:

- This work presents QBT-MAC that supports priority of the data packets i.e., periodic (low priority) and event-based (high priority).
- QBT-MAC has a packet queuing mechanism that allows sender nodes to choose an appropriate queue according to packet priority.
- The burst transmission technique allows successful transmission of queued packet to optimize the performance.
- The performance of QBT-MAC is conducted using real-world solar irradiance data for 48 consecutive hours, and is compared with QPPD-MAC [6] and EEM-MAC [9] in terms of average delay, packet delivery ratio (PDR) and energy efficiency.
- The simulation results indicate that the QBT-MAC achieves better performance in terms of average delay PDR, and energy efficiency.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses related works. Section III describes the proposed QBT-MAC protocol. Section IV defines the performance evaluation and presents the results. Finally, Section V concludes the work and provides the future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

The MAC protocols for ambient IoT follow three approaches, namely sender-initiated, receiver-initiated and sink initiated [10]. In the literature, a large number of protocols have used receiver-initiated in which the receiver initiates the communication. There are many protocols which offer various features and can be implemented for different applications. For instance, the protocol presented in [8] incorporates harvested energy information to adjust the beacon interval and sensing time to improve performance. The research work in [9] sets the duty cycle according to available energy and achieves load balancing among devices. This allows high energy device to wake up more frequently and receives more data packets in the network. Authors in [11] presented a mechanism that sets different duty cycle level according to remaining energy of the device. The work presented in [12] supports QoS and regulates the active period based on network traffic conditions to maximize the performance. The scheme in [13] incorporates both energy harvesting and node mobility aspects, and ensures sustainable network operation. In [4], authors introduced data transmission and data processing mechanisms to address the data accumulation issue and optimize the data transmission rate in the network. The scheme presented in [14] allows devices to access the channel using different contending priorities based on available harvested energy. The model in [15] introduces a transmission policy according to the current energy level. The model enables nodes to increase the amount of data transfer under high energy harvesting conditions. The QoS-aware protocol in [6] supports multi-priority of data and sets the listening time according to the stored energy level. Furthermore, it supports the highest priority packet by minimizing the delay, and conserves energy to avoid any disruption in low harvesting conditions. The scheme in [16] incorporates the available energy to adjust the listening time of the node and selects the cluster nodes accordingly. Nevertheless, the primary focus of existing QoS-aware protocols is to reduce the delay for the highest priority data packets. However, the lower priority packets are generally neglected, resulting in longer delays and packet loss, which is undesirable for overall network performance. Therefore,

there is a need to develop a QoS-aware protocol for ambient IoT that can support both types of data packets and can provide better overall performance under dynamic energy harvesting conditions.

III. QBT-MAC PROTOCOL

This section describes QBT-MAC's communication overview and priority assignment, packet queuing and burst transmission technique, respectively.

A. Communication overview and priority assignment

QBT-MAC follows the receiver-initiated approach in which the receiver initiates the communication, as shown in Fig. 1. According to this paradigm, the receiver wakes up periodically according to its energy level and broadcasts a special control packet, named the wake-up beacon (B). Then, it continues listening to the channel until maximum T_w duration for incoming small Tx beacons (TxB) which contain sender and packet priority (P) information. P value is determined by the sender's application according to the type of data packet. For the explanation purpose, P can be 1 or 2 for low priority and high priority packets, respectively. The receiver adjusts T_w timer according to received P value from TxB. It cancels T_w timer when TxB with highest P value i.e., 2, is received. Otherwise, it keeps listening to the channel and waits for other TxB to arrive or until T_w timer expires. After that, the receiver transmits a RxB beacon that includes the address of the selected sender, which proceeds to send the data packet. This is then followed by acknowledgement (ACK) packet. QBT-MAC follows the similar duty cycle mechanism and structure of wake-up, Tx, Rx and ACK packets, as specified in QPPD-MAC [6].

B. Packet queuing and burst data transmission technique

The sender device uses two different queues to support QoS and assigns appropriate queue to the arrived packet based on maximum tolerable delay, which is application dependent. Q_1 and Q_2 are queues to store the low and high priority packets, respectively. The data packet in Q_2 has short tolerable delay, thus, it must be transmitted immediately to meet the application requirement. On the other hand, packet arrived in Q_1 has a higher tolerable delay and thus they can

Figure 1. Basic communication overview between a transmitter and receiver. The sender node has two different priority queues Q_1 and Q_2 and it selects the queue based on data type, P_2 packet in Q_2 , and least priority, P_1 packet in Q_1 .

be sent when Q_2 is empty. The sender node after receiving the wake-up beacon, first checks Q_2 queue and then Q_1 queue, if there is any packet. If sender device holds a packet, it senses the channel and transmits a TxB that indicates as a request for channel access. The higher number of sender devices leads to more packets in the queue. In addition, the channel remains busy as all devices are trying to access the same channel for packet transmission. As a result, packets in Q_1 experiences further delays, and exceeding the buffer limit will cause packet loss in the network. To address this issue, QBT-MAC introduces a burst data transmission technique that supports buffered packets. In this technique, after completion of a successful data transmission, the receiver node stays active for a short period of time, referred as dwell time (T_D), and listens for incoming new packets. Both T_D and T_w timer values are application dependent and can be tuned. This allows sender nodes to transmit all queued packet in one burst to reduce overall packet delay and packet loss in the network.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The performance of QBT-MAC is evaluated using GreenCastalia [17] that supports simulation of ambient IoT rechargeable batteries. In the simulation, we have taken parameters of commercial solar cell of size (A) 7.7 cm^2 that has a panel efficiency (η) of 22%, CC2420 radio, TelosB as IoT device. The harvested solar energy, E_h per slot is computed as [18]:

$$E_h = A \times \eta \times I_s \times d_s, \quad (1)$$

where I_s and d_s represents solar irradiance (W/m^2), and duration of a timeslot in seconds, respectively. The latest NREL [19] real-life solar traces are used for a more realistic harvesting conditions. Furthermore, the network topology consists of 7 IoT-TelosB nodes which are randomly distributed and the receiver node is located at the center as shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, QBT-MAC can be further optimized for a large sensor network that supports several smaller-sized networks, called clusters. Each IoT-TelosB device generates a data packet every 5 minutes, and assigns the packet priority based on a random number between 0 and 1. If the number is less than 0.25, it assigns high priority P_2 and selects Q_2 queue. Else, it allocates the low priority P_1 and is inserted into Q_1 . All devices follow p -persistent CSMA to forward their data packets to the receiver. Table I shows the simulation parameters.

Figure 2. Network topology.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Simulation time	48 h
A	7.7 cm^2
η	22 %
I_s	Variable
Timeslots	24/day
E_{max}	3672J
Sender nodes	1 to 7
Coverage area	$30 \text{ m} \times 30 \text{ m}$
TelosB operating voltage	2.1 V
Packet size	28 bytes
Size of TxB	14 bytes
Size of RxB	13 bytes
Size of ACK	11 bytes
Size of wake-up beacon (B)	9 bytes
T_w	5 ms
T_D	5 ms
Slot time	0.32 ms

The dynamic nature of ambient source, such as high solar irradiance during the daytime allows the device to harvest sufficient energy. Fig. 3 shows that the harvested energy reaches the peak value of 584.87J and 617.195J in the afternoon on the first and second day, respectively. During the night, external energy is not available; hence, the device utilizes the stored energy to continue its operation.

The QBT-MAC follows same duty cycle mechanism of QPPD-MAC [6] that adjusts the wake up schedule according to the available energy, as shown in Fig. 4. The result demonstrates that the device increases its duty cycle, d_c when sufficient energy is available, as given in Eq (2). This allows node to reduce sleep time, T_{sleep} to maximize the performance.

$$d_c = \frac{RE_{total} - E_{th}}{100\% - E_{th}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. Average hourly harvested energy from solar for two consecutive days.

Figure 4. d_c value based on remaining energy, RE_{total} .

$$T_{sleep} = \frac{T_{listen} \times (1 - d_c)}{d_c}, \quad (3)$$

where RE_{total} , T_{listen} and E_{th} represents total energy, listen time, and threshold energy (10%).

Next, the performance of QBT-MAC is discussed in terms of average packet delay, PDR and energy efficiency, which are primary concerns for QoS application.

The average delay performance of QBT-MAC is presented in Fig. 5. The result is almost the same for all protocols at lower number of sender devices. The reason is that when the number of sender devices is 1-4, the sender devices face low hindrance in accessing the medium, resulting in, both queues remaining almost empty. Nevertheless, when the number of sender devices is higher i.e., 5-7, QBT-MAC reduces the delay significantly by up to 69.26% and 53.94% when compared with QPPD-MAC and EEM-MAC, respectively. This is because, after the completion of successful transmission, the receiver stays active for T_D , and waits for incoming packets. Consequently,

Figure 5. Average packet delay of all packets vs. number of sender nodes.

Figure 6. Average delay of low priority, P_1 packets vs. number of sender nodes.

the sender device uses burst transmission technique that allows transfer of queued packets consecutively, when the channel is free. Therefore, the use of burst transmission technique helps to achieve significant reduction in delay for low priority packets, P_1 , which is shown in Fig. 6, that contributed to the overall reduction of average delay performance. The delay for high priority P_2 is almost the same for both QBT-MAC and QPPD-MAC, hence, it is not shown.

PDR results for all three protocols are shown in Fig. 7. The graph shows that QBT-MAC achieves better PDR performance of up to 15.86% when compared with others. This is because of packet queuing and burst data transmission techniques that support both high and low priority data to maximize overall application performance. QPPD-MAC allows single transmission per cycle and as a result, sender nodes face significant delay in accessing the channel. This causes the maximum buffer limit to be exceeded and caused packet loss in the network.

Figure 7. PDR comparison with varying number of sender nodes.

Figure 8. Comparison of energy consumption per bit with varying number of sender nodes.

In EEM-MAC, the receiver does not account for packet priority, hence sender device faces less delay in accessing the channel, and as a result, it gives low packet loss compared to QPPD-MAC.

The energy consumption per bit, also known as energy efficiency, is shown in Fig. 8. It is the ratio of total consumed energy to the number packet transmitted. The result shows that QBT-MAC has lower energy consumption per bit of up to 13.6% and 1.5% when compared with QPPD-MAC and EEM-MAC, respectively. This is because the total energy consumption is almost the same in all protocols. Nevertheless, the number of transmitted packets in QBT-MAC, as shown in Figure 7 is higher than the others, and as a result, it outperforms in terms of energy efficiency.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a QoS-aware MAC protocol for ambient IoT, called QBT-MAC, that considers different priority data packets. In QBT-MAC, each sender device has two queues, and it schedules the data transmission according to the type of queued packet. On the other hand, sender devices use burst transmission technique to transmit queued packet consecutively to maximize the application performance. QBT-MAC performance evaluation was conducted using real-life solar irradiance data and compared with two other MAC protocols. The simulation results show that QBT-MAC provides superior QoS performance in terms of average delay, packet delivery ratio, and energy efficiency. Future work includes extending this work for battery-less IoT.

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REFERENCES

- [1] X. Yu, K. Ergun, X. Song, L. Cherkasova, and T. Š. Rosing, "Automating and Optimizing Reliability-Driven Deployment in Energy-Harvesting IoT Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 787-799, 2022.
- [2] G. Moloudian *et al.*, "RF Energy Harvesting Techniques for Battery-less Wireless Sensing, Industry 4.0 and Internet of Things: A Review," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 5732 - 5745, 2024.
- [3] M. M. Sandhu, S. Khalifa, R. Jurdak, and M. Portmann, "Task scheduling for energy-harvesting-based IoT: A survey and critical analysis," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 18, pp. 13825-13848, 2021.
- [4] R. Wang, W. Li, F. Gao, and T. Jiao, "The PSL MAC Protocol for Accumulated Data Processing in the Energy-Harvesting Wireless Sensor Network," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2022, pp. 1-10, 2022.
- [5] P. Kaur, P. Singh, and B. S. Sohi, "Adaptive MAC protocol for solar energy harvesting based wireless sensor networks in agriculture," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 111, no. 4, pp. 2263-2285, 2020.
- [6] S. Sarang, M. Driberg, A. Awang, and R. Ahmad, "A QoS MAC protocol for prioritized data in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks," *Computer networks*, vol. 144, pp. 141-153, 2018.
- [7] G. Famitafreshi, M. S. Afaqui, and J. Melià-Seguí, "A comprehensive review on energy harvesting integration in IoT systems from MAC layer perspective: Challenges and opportunities," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 9, p. 3097, 2021.
- [8] X. Fafoutis and N. Dragoni, "ODMAC: An on-demand MAC protocol for energy harvesting-wireless sensor networks," in *Proceedings of the 8th ACM Symposium on Performance evaluation of wireless ad hoc, sensor, and ubiquitous networks*, New York, USA, 2011, pp. 49-56.
- [9] A. Bengheni, F. Didi, and I. Bambrik, "EEM-EHWSN: Enhanced energy management scheme in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks," *Wireless Networks*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 3029-3046, 2019.
- [10] H. H. R. Sherazi, L. A. Grieco, and G. Boggia, "A comprehensive review on energy harvesting MAC protocols in WSNs: Challenges and tradeoffs," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 71, pp. 117-134, 2018.
- [11] A. Bengheni, "A multi-threshold energy approach for energy harvesting WSN," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on New Technologies of Information and Communication (NTIC)*, Mila, Algeria, 2022, pp. 1-5.
- [12] T. D. Nguyen, J. Y. Khan, and D. T. Ngo, "An adaptive MAC protocol for RF energy harvesting wireless sensor networks," in *Proceedings of IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, Washington, USA, 2016, pp. 1-6: IEEE.
- [13] Z. Hmidi, L. Kahloul, and S. Benharzallah, "A new mobility and energy harvesting aware medium access control (meh-mac) protocol: Modelling and performance evaluation," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 142, p. 103108, 2023.
- [14] Y. Liu, Z. Yang, R. Yu, Y. Xiang, and S. Xie, "An efficient MAC protocol with adaptive energy harvesting for machine-to-machine networks," *IEEE access*, vol. 3, pp. 358-367, 2015.
- [15] K. Charoenchaiprakit, W. Piyarat, and K. Woradit, "Optimal data transfer of SEH-WSN node via MDP based on duty cycle and battery energy," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 82947-82965, 2021.
- [16] K. Shim and H.-K. Park, "Priority-based pipelined-forwarding MAC protocol for EH-WSNs," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2019, pp. 1-7, 2019.
- [17] D. Benedetti, C. Petrioli, and D. Spenza, "GreenCastalia: An energy-harvesting-enabled framework for the Castalia simulator," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Energy Neutral Sensing Systems*, 2013, pp. 1-6.
- [18] A. Cammarano, C. Petrioli, and D. Spenza, "Online energy harvesting prediction in environmentally powered wireless sensor networks," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 16, no. 17, pp. 6793-6804, 2016.
- [19] National Renewable Energy Laboratory., Last Accessed April, 2024, https://midcdmz.nrel.gov/oahu_archive.